

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B170
Date: 11 Feb 2006
Take Off 09:54:47
Landing: 14:53:35
Flight Time 4h58m48s

Campaign: DODO
Trials Instructions: Biomass / Aerosol Sampling
Operating Area: South of Dakar, over ocean

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Graham Morgan	BAES
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Simon Osborne	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	VACC / PAN / WAS	Jim McQuaid	University of Leeds
7	CCN / CVI / CCM2	Paul James	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
9	Filters	Alison Perry	FAAM
10	AMS 2	Paul Williams	University of Manchester
11	Wet Neph	James Bowles	Met Office
12	Core Chemistry	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
13	Mission Scientist Training	Ben Johnson	Met Office
14	SWS / SHIMS	Ian Rule	Met Office
15	ARIES	Alan Vance	Met Office
16	Mission Scientist 2	Hugh Coe	University of Manchester
17			
18			

Flight Track:

B170 Track 11-FEB-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b170

Date: 11 Feb 2006

Project: DODO

Location: South of Dakar over ocean

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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094139		INU to navigate	-.03 kft	334	
094541		taxy start	-.03 kft	334	
094706		asp open	-.03 kft	106	
095447		T/O	-.03 kft	353	from Dakar, P1 Start
095447	101121	Profile 1	-.03 - 16.0 kft	335	
101122	101859	Profile 2	16.0 - 9.5 kft	180	
101900	103400	Run 1.1	9.5 kft	178	
102522		bbr open	9.5 kft	178	
103401	104504	Profile 3	9.5 - -.02 kft	182	
103919		rate of descent chan	3.8 kft	180	
104504	104848	Profile 4	-.02 - 1.9 kft	175	qnh 1018
105334	110837	Run 2.1	1.9 kft	312	bbrs exposed at start
110942	111426	Run 2.2	1.9 kft	049	
111506	113006	Run 2.3	1.9 kft	136	tapes changed 11:29
113105	113602	Run 2.4	1.9 kft	044	
113720	115530	Run 2.5	1.9 kft	308	strange sea/water layer observed at 11:39
115608	120056	Profile 5	1.9 - 4.5 kft	352	
120834	122339	Run 3.1	4.5 kft	144	
122434	122935	Run 3.2	4.5 kft	231	
123027	124506	Run 3.3	4.5 kft	320	
124629	125129	Run 3.4	4.5 kft	225	
125226	130720	Run 3.5	4.5 kft	142	tapes change 13:02
130759	131419	Profile 6	4.5 - 8.4 kft	174	
130928		Profile 6	6.0 kft	174	interrupt
131045		Profile 6	6.0 kft	064	resume
131149		Profile 6	7.0 kft	066	interrupt
131251		Profile 6	7.0 kft	327	resume
131419	133035	Run 4.1	8.4 kft	325	
133137	133637	Run 4.2	8.4 kft	052	
133748	135248	Run 4.3	8.4 kft	143	
135352	135852	Run 4.4	8.4 kft	050	
135946	141448	Run 4.5	8.4 kft	324	
141639	142020	Profile 7	8.4 - 12.0 kft	330	
142039	143328	Profile 8	12.0 - -.01 kft	359	
142909		Profile 8	2.5 kft	002	rate of descent change at 3kft
143328	143824	Profile 9	-.01 - 5.0 kft	005	
145335		Land	0.01 kft	355	at Dakar
145934		standstill	0.02 kft	329	14'44.56N, 17'29.30W

B170 Track 11-FEB-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

DODO Flight: In situ sampling of biomass and dust aerosol, cloud processing of aerosol

Flight No: B170

Date: 11th February 2006

Trial objectives:

In situ sampling of aged biomass, potentially after cloud processing. Model validation of dust and biomass plumes.

Location:

Over ocean to south of Dakar, in region west of airway UG853 and in region defined by:

A: Limel

B: 11,13N; 017,20W

Weather:

Clear skies preferred.

Special requirements:

Low-level (50ft) flying over ocean. Open air sample pipes in taxi before take-off.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Dakar.
2. Profile ascent to FL150 at 1000ft/min towards Limel, south of Dakar [20 mins, T= 20 mins]
3. Profile descent to within the aerosol layer at 1000ft/min [10 mins, T=30mins]
4. Perform a SLR within the aerosol layer to point A [10mins, T=40mins]
5. Starting from A, perform a profile descent at 1000ft/min above 3000ft, 500ft/min below to 50ft towards point B. [15 mins, T=55mins]
6. Perform a procedural turn in the region of point B and ascend to first aerosol level to be defined by aircraft scientist. [5 mins, T=60 mins]
7. Perform a 15 minute SLR within the aerosol on heading 330°. [15 mins, T= 75 mins]
8. Turn 90 deg clockwise and perform a 5 min SLR [5 mins, T=80 mins]
9. Turn 90 deg clockwise and perform a 15 min SLR on heading 150° [15 mins, T=95 mins]
10. Turn 90 deg clockwise and perform a 5 min SLR [5 mins, T=100 mins]
11. Turn 90 deg clockwise and perform a 15 min SLR on heading 330° [15 mins, T=115 mins]
12. Ascend to the next aerosol layer. Perform a procedural turn onto a reciprocal heading and perform a 15 min SLR at new level [20mins, T=135mins]
13. Turn 90 deg clockwise and perform a 5 min SLR [5 mins, T=140 mins]
14. Turn 90 deg clockwise and perform a 15 min SLR [15 mins, T=155 mins]
15. Turn 90 deg clockwise and perform a 5 min SLR [5 mins, T=160 mins]
16. Turn 90 deg clockwise and perform a 15 min SLR [15 mins, T=175 mins]
17. Ascend to the next aerosol layer. Perform a procedural turn onto a reciprocal heading and perform a 15 min SLR at new level [20mins, T=195mins]
18. Repeat steps 9-12 at new level [40 mins, T=235 mins]
19. Perform an SLR at a level to be determined by the aircraft scientist back towards Dakar [40 mins, T=275 mins]
20. Land Dakar.

Mission Scientist De-brief sheet

Flight B170

11th February 2006

Summary of the weather conditions

Band of medium and upper level cloud, the northern end of which running through the Dakar region SW to NE. Clear skies to the north of Dakar over sea areas, but clean of aerosol. This cloud affecting the operating region to the south of Dakar.

Aims of sortie

To make in-situ microphysical and chemical sampling of cloud-processed biomass burning aerosol.

Summary of the flight

A successful sortie was conducted over sea areas to the south of Dakar. No decent radiation measurements were made however, due to excessively cloudy conditions. Two points were defined pre-flight:

Point A (LIMEL):

Point B :

These two points comprised opposite corners of a box within which we carried out raster patterns at various altitudes.

The take off from Niamey constituted the start of profile P1 which topped out at FL160 heading south to point A. The top of the aerosol and strong hydrolapse was found at FL115. Shallow Cu clouds were bubbling up out of this upper aerosol layer. After a profile descent to FL095 (with a few short penetrations of cu clouds) a run was carried out within the upper biomass burning plume to point A. A profile descent was then made from point A to point B down to 50ft. There was significant whitecapping with winds 20+ kts. The profile identified three distinct biomass burning plumes. Raster patterns were then performed within these biomass plumes at the following altitudes:

- (i) 2000ft (working towards point A)
- (ii) 4500ft (working towards point B)
- (iii) FL084 (working towards point A)

The long (nominally 15 min) SLRs of the raster ran roughly on 320deg and 140deg headings. These legs were separated by (nominally) 5 min legs. Filters were exposed on each of the long runs during the rasters (except the very last run, R4.5) Clear slots were visible between the different aerosol layers. The neph data showed that the marine boundary layer (very shallow at around 1700ft) contained measurable levels of sea salt. Aerosol loadings and CO concentrations were quite variable throughout the first raster. AMS, neph, PCASP (600-1100/cc), SID, and ozone and CO (135-200 ppbv) correlation data indicated that this aerosol was biomass burning aerosol with no evidence of dust. There were numerous sea fishing vessels within the LIMEL (point A) area.

CO levels at 4500ft were upto 220 ppbv with aerosol concs (PCASP) at least as high as at 2000ft. Some large changes were seen on the ozone and CO but with no concurrent change in the aerosol or neph values.

At FL084, there were measurable values on the NO_x. PCASP concs were again similar to the lower plumes. In all three rasters, aerosol loadings were higher towards the southwest (point B) relative to the northeast (point A). Certainly at FL084, there was quite an abrupt change on the raster legs. Uncorrected single scatter albedos within the heavier aerosol loadings were about 0.75. Between 6 and 7 oktas of cloud (altocu and Ci) were present above during the rasters.

After the completion of the third raster at LIMEL, a profile ascent was made from FL084 to FL120 above the aerosol plume. A profile descent on the way to Dakar going north was then made down to 50ft. A highly structured atmosphere was again found in terms of the humidity and aerosol profiles.

Clear slots and dark biomass burning plumes were clearly visible out of the window. The most marked clear slot was at around 1900ft just above the marine boundary where the neph scatter coeffs went to zero and visibility was very high with a blue horizon. A profile climb was made from 50ft to FL050 where the clear slot was again observed. A good hit was seen on the Nox (3 ppbv) during this climb that may have been a ship plume rather than biomass burning aerosol.

Instrument faults

Wet neph: problem logging both neph data streams via Labview on the laptop; therefore neph2 was recorded onto the laptop and neph1 was recorded onto HORACE only.

ARIES: overheating; noise problems; software glitches. But still reliable data for a good chunk of the flight.

AMS: data logging problem at start; data recorded throughout rasters, but noise excessive at times.

S.R. Osborne
12/02/06

Aircraft Scientist's Log

AS = SIMON OSBORNE

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Date **11/02/06**

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LIMEL
10327

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0954	P17	Off!!		Profile from take-off	T/O NIAMEY AIRFIELD
		1000 ft (in climb above 2000 ft)			1/8 cloud cover, different levels above but some low cloud at 10000 ft
		2000' FL090 FL100			in ascent. PMSF + Nept
10040		FL110			Part 2 in ascent CO ~ 25000 ft
		FL115			Thin clouds above 78 sun Inversion & Cu at top of ascent good clearance.
1009		FL140			cloud density about alt - but start to run over Cu field.
101120	P1A	FL160	180	13.7N 17.4W	2nd profile climb / start descent thin cloud v. little - top of Cu.
	P2V	FL117			thin cloud v. little cloud-free AMS logging problem
101900	P1	FL095	178	13.2N 17.4W	Start run in top of plume below Cu level plume structure vertical different layer PMSF ~ 9000 ft. 7/8 cloud above. CO ~ 25000 ft. $T_{sp} \approx 90 \times 10^6$ mi
1028					wet rep not recording at present several fairly uniform along run CO dropping off a little
103320	P1	FL095			several + clean dropping off now
103359	P1	FL095 FL075	182	12.2N 17.3W	FL075 run / start descent to 5000 ft comes dropping off now. v. hazy sky all around. some whitecaps.

- ① 2000'
- ② 4500'
- ③ 8400'

Aircraft Scientist's Log

AMS OK from L1M2 of words.

Flight No **B...120**
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Date **11/02/06**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
103240		4500'	180		peak peak in sight.
		4000'			change to 500 ft/min.
		3000'			cones dropping off. 7/8 cloud cover
104227		2000'			Encounter in sight - MBL → good pass
					wind 20 kts. Quite a few caps
104503	P3 → P4	50'	176	11.5 17.3	End profile descent (start climb).
		1000'			Can see blue horizon at this height
104848		2000'	180	11.3 17.3	End profile climb, wait for (B) good vis.
					Good overall layer. CO ~ 200 ppbv
105114					In turn - below MBL cloud
105333	R2-1	2000'	312	11.2 17.3	CO cal done in re-positioning. Start run → just PASSED.
110000					(better in this leg) → a bit later night no MBL cloud along run.
					cones dropping along run.
1103					Some plume-like structures.
1105					PASP 200 - 1190/10 along run. MBL cloud just off to the left.
110837	R2-1	2000'		11.8 17.9	end run (FLIGHTS over.)
110942	R2-2	2000'	050	11.9 17.8	Start run (start run) → D
					v. plummy - bit swirling, steady.
					CO: 135 - 200 ppbv.
111424	R2-2	2000'	069	12.0 17.6	End run - is it here.
111500	R2-3	2000'	138	12.0 17.5	Start run next leg of R2-3
					good correlation O ₃ + CO. 1510 MBS
					PASP 600 - 800/10. s.i.d. (10-20)
112720					cones fairly steady during this run if.
113007	R2-3	2000'	138	11.5 17.0	End Run.

30.05' Hz
1018
QNT.

SS: 4-5

After 10:50
later!

B → A

C → D

D → E

NO DUST!

AMS → organic + sulfate + nitrate

R2-1

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
113104	R2.4	2000'	046	11.3 16.9w	Start run (short leg) 7/8 cloud above. Med + high level Surface winds similar SS=4-5
1135					V. gentle turn left to keep out of Carriera airspace.
113601	R2.4	2000'	034	11.5 16.2	End short run
113716	R2.5	2000'	308	11.6 16.7	Start run F → L last leg of 1st pass but dropping the ground Neph Gsp fairly steady over mountain lots of skipping below us → fishing
113900					
1148		2000'		12.0 17.1	plume structure once again. out of plume base winds low now (~12000)
115500					
115531	R2.5	2000'	325	12.4 17.4	short run a 1st pass 500 ft/min.
115600	P4.7	2000'	352	12.4 17.4	Start profile climbs to next layer back into plume proper. can see 2 brown aerosol layers clear slot. Alth Cu above 6-7/8
		~2300'			
		~3000'			
		3200'			
120015		4100'			Base of next layer?
		4500'			End profile climbs to next level. plume in weather lens.
120834	R3.1	4500'	144	12.4 17.4	Start run (early) good. con ~22000 in weather plume
					Pass up to 9500cc → HSD
122130					" " 1150/cc
122300	R3.1	4500'		11.7 16.8	End run. + right turn.
122433	R3.2	4500'	232	11.6 16.8	start short run.
122933	R3.2	4500'	230	11.4 17.1	End run. + right turn.
123026	R3.3	4500'	320	11.4 17.1	Start run mid pitch E → D

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Date **11/02/06**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1239					Large slip + plane to left.
					CO + O ₃ correlated, @ 1235 = large ^{aerosol} step change, but no signature.
1240					coming under Cu fields over
1242					Now aerosol + trace gas correlation
124340					upper cloud thinning now.
124505	R3.3	4500'	319	12.2 17.7	End run (left turn)
124629	R3.4	4500'	228	12.1 17.8	Start run (short one)
125128	R3.4	4500'	229	11.9 18.0	End Run. (+ left turn)
125219	R3.5	4500'	142	11.9 18.0	Start run (last leg of 2 nd EAST) ^(?)
					PEASL ~ 700/cc. CO ~ 210 ppbv.
1256					ARIES going down due to resist ^(?)
125620					Tr. ^{MBL} Cu to our ^{front} right
	R3.5				End S. Run at BRAVO
	P67	4500'		11.0 17.4	Start profile climb to 4000' ^(?)
130927	P67	FLO60		11.0 17.4	Interrupt climb to turn.
131043	P67	FLO60	064	11.0 17.3	re-start ^(with in 10 min) profile climb ^(?) 6/8 cloud ^(?)
131148	P67	FLO70	066	11.0 17.2	Interrupt profile climb again.
131250	P67	FLO70	324	11.1 17.2	re-start profile climb.
131415	P67	FLO84	325	11.2 17.3	End climb / start Run B → C
					Now signal too! Can see near top ^(?) of aerosol ^(?) here
					PEASL ~ 900/cc. CO ~ 250 ppbv.
1329					out of ^{high} aerosol layer now.
133034	R4.1	FLO84	318	12.1 18.0	End run (extended for bag filling)
133136		FLO84	051		Start run (short leg)

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.1.70**.....
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Date **11/02/06**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
133636	R42	R084	051	12.3 17.7	End run (short) + right turn.
133748	R43	R084	141	12.3 17.7	Start run PCTSP steady at 6000
13491					Hitting thicker aerosol again. gusty PCTSP ~ 1000/c (0.240 ppbv)
					skin messy cloud above 7/8 cover.
135120					Duffing left a bit.
135242		R084	151	11.4 17.1	End run going south; left turn.
135368	R44	R084	050	11.4 17.1	Start run (short leg)
135510					Good peak in PCTSP (1400/c) + CO (280 ppb)
					~ 2 ppbv NO _x ; ~ 10 ₂ but no NO.
135850	R44	R084	051	11.6 16.8	End short run - v. good structure
135945	R45	R084	319	11.6 16.8	Start run (last leg of 3 rd PCTSP)
140350					Use ^{0.55} $\approx 100 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$. $\tau_{\text{PCTSP}} \approx 33 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}$ $\tau_{\text{CO}} \approx 0.75$
1412					CO cal ⁿ start.
141444	R45	R084	322	12.4 17.4	End run, end of PCTSP
141638	P7	R084	330	12.5 17.5	Start probe climb. to above aerosol
141910		R100			top of aerosol layer
142019	P7	R120	000	12.7 17.5	End probe climb.
142038	P8	R120	357	12.8 17.5	Start probe descent
		R100			Back in Biomass plume.
		3350'			= very clean str.
		3000'			= lower aerosol layer → v. dark
		1800'			another clean layer → need to look out to 7000
					→ in MBL now.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B170

Date: 11/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:54:47																Start Profile 1 from Take-off	
09:58:24	60	0.11	Off													FL030	
09:59:36	10	0.11	Off													FL040	
10:00:54	10	0.11	Off													FL050	
10:01:51	5	0.11	0													FL060	
10:02:45	260	0.11		5	1											FL070	
10:03:44	480	0.10		10												FL080	
10:04:42	810	0.10		20	1											FL090	
10:05:40	700	0.10		15	1											FL100	
10:06:42	400	0.10		5	1											FL110	
10:07:50	30	0.11														FL120	
10:08:41	15	0.13														FL130	
10:09:33	7	0.13														FL140	
10:10:24	12	0.14														FL150	
10:11:21	8	0.14														End of Profile 1 & Start Profile 2 @ FL160	
10:12:14	15	0.12														FL150	
10:13:15	25	0.12														FL140	
10:14:21	120	0.11		5	Noise											FL130	
10:15:51	260	0.10	5	5	1											FL120	
10:17:10	300	0.10	8	5	1											FL110	
10:19:01	1100	0.10		20	2											End of Profile 2 & Start Run 1 @ FL095	
10:20:00	980	0.10		20	1												
10:22:00	900	0.10	9	20	2												
10:24:00	1060	0.10		20	1												
10:26:00	1100	0.10		20	4												
10:28:00	930	0.10		20	4												
10:30:00	880	0.10		20	2												
10:32:00	700	0.10		20	4												
10:34:03																End of Run 1 & Start Profile 3 from FL095	
10:34:35	1080	0.10		20	5											FL090	
10:35:23	540	0.10		10	1											FL080	
10:36:17	550	0.10		10	1											FL070	
10:37:18	710	0.10		10	10											FL060	
10:38:18	1100	0.10		10	3											FL050	
10:39:04	700	0.10	Off	10	4											FL040	
10:40:43	800	0.09	Off	10	10											FL030	
10:42:10	930	0.10	Off	10	4											FL020	
10:43:28	150	0.09	Off	5	Noise											FL010	
10:45:05	130	0.09	Off	20	Noise											End of Profile 3 & Start Profile 4 @ 50'	
10:46:57	100	0.09	Off	10	Noise											FL010	
10:48:52	1100	0.10	Off	10	10											End of Profile 4 @ 2000'	
10:53:38																Start Run 2.1 @ 2000'	
10:54:00	1100	0.09	Off	10	1												
10:56:00	1000	0.09	Off	10	1												
10:58:00	1000	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:00:00	760	0.09	Off	10	1												

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B170

Date: 11/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:02:00	670	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:04:00	760	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:06:00	500	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:08:00	700	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:08:38																End of Run 2.1 @ FL2000'	
11:09:42																Start Run 2.2 @ 2000'	
11:10:00	500	0.09	Off	5	1												
11:12:00	830	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:14:26																End of Run 2.1	
11:15:07																Start Run 2.3 @ 2000'	
11:16:00	500	0.09	Off	5	1												
11:18:00	800	0.09	Off	10	2												
11:20:00	850	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:22:00	750	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:24:00	950	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:26:00	880	0.09	Off	10	2												
11:28:00	850	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:30:07																End of Run 2.3	
11:31:05																Start Run 2.4 @ 2000'	
11:32:00	740	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:34:00	650	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:36:03																End of Run 2.4	
11:37:18																Start Run 2.5 @ 2000'	
11:38:00	660	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:40:00	670	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:42:00	700	0.09	Off	10	2												
11:44:00	600	0.09	Off	10	2												
11:46:00	780	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:48:00	700	0.09	Off	10	2												
11:50:00	670	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:52:00	720	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:54:00	380	0.09	Off	10	1												
11:55:31																End of Run 2.5	
11:56:11																Start Profile 5 from 2000'	
11:57:48	220	0.09	Off	5	1											FL030	
12:00:57	545	0.10	Off	5	1											End of Profile 5 @ FL045	
12:08:35																Start Run 3.1 @ FL045	
12:09:00	750	0.10	Off	10	1												
12:11:00	950	0.10	Off	10	1												
12:13:00	880	0.10	Off	10	3												
12:15:00	940	0.10	Off	10	3												
12:17:00	980	0.10	Off	15	3												
12:19:00	1100	0.09	Off	15	5												
12:21:00	1160	0.09	Off	15	3												
12:23:00	1100	0.09	Off	15	3												
12:23:39																End of Run 3.1	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B170

Date: 11/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:24:36																Start Run 3.2 @ FL045	
12:25:00	1080	0.10	Off	10	3												
12:27:00	1190	0.09	Off	10													
12:29:36																End of Run 3.2	
12:30:29																Start Run 3.3 @ FL045	
12:31:00	1150	0.09	Off	10	3												
12:33:00	1080	0.09	Off	10	2												
12:35:00	1020	0.09	Off	10	2												
12:37:00	1010	0.10	Off	10	1												
12:39:00	980	0.10	Off	15	1												
12:41:00	920	0.10	Off	10	1												
12:43:00	890	0.10	Off	10	1												
12:45:07																End of Run 3.3	
12:46:31																Start Run 3.4 @ FL045	
12:47:00	720	0.10	Off	10	1												
12:49:00	710	0.10	Off	10	1												
12:51:32																End of Run 3.4	
12:52:21																Start Run 3.5 @ FL045	
12:53:00	600	0.10	Off	15	2												
12:55:00	900	0.10	Off	15	3												
12:57:00	920	0.10	Off	15	2												
12:59:00	930	0.10	Off	15	2												
13:01:00	980	0.10	Off	15	3												
13:03:00	1090	0.10	Off	20	2												
13:05:00	1000	0.09	Off	20	5												
13:07:21																End of Run 3.5	
13:08:01																Start Profile 6 from FL045	
13:09:29	890	0.09	Off	20	Noise											FL060	
13:11:58	1050	0.09	Off	20	2											FL070	
13:14:17																End of Profile 6 & Start Run 4.1 @ FL084	
13:15:00	1100	0.10	Off	20	2												
13:17:00	900	0.10	Off	10	2												
13:19:00	940	0.10	Off	20	2												
13:21:00	930	0.10	Off	20	2												
13:23:00	900	0.10	Off	15	1												
13:25:00	975	0.10	Off	15	1												
13:27:00	730	0.10	Off	15	2												
13:30:35																End of Run 4.1	
13:31:43																Start Run 4.2 @ FL084	
13:32:00	710	0.10	Off	15	2												
13:34:00	630	0.10	Off	10	2												
13:36:39																End of Run 4.2	
13:37:51																Start Run 4.3 @ FL084	
13:38:00	610	0.10	Off	10	2												
13:40:00	610	0.10	Off	10	2												
13:42:00	880	0.10	Off	20	3												

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: Bnnn

Date: DD/MM/YY

C) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	X	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	X	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	X X	
4) Log on to FLOODS	X	
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	X	
6) In PVWAVE	X	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X	
ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE	X	
a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat	X	
b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat	X	
iii) exit	X	Zero bad blocks
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE	X	Don't worry about lots of FORTRAN run-time errors as long as the program continues. These are format errors when writing to ascii files.
a) Default directory: PMSDATA:	X	
b) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat	X	
d) Comment string:	X	
e) Start time: 0 if unknown	X	
f) End time: 240000 if unknown	X	
g) Read 2DC: Y	X	
h) Read 2DP: Y	X	
i) Secondary data Y	X	
j) FSP-SYNC: Y	X	
k) cmd.str: Y	X	
l) Auto time correction: N	X	
m) Full length secondary: N	X	
8) 2D image display and printing		This section is optional
Quick look at image blocks if required		
In PVWAVE		
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'		
i) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY		
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:		
b) Flight number: Bnnn		
c) IWC plot: N		
d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP		
e) Start time: 0 if unknown		
f) End time: 240000 if unknown		
g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)

Preparation of imagery for Core data product		
iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks <p style="text-align: center;">10</p> iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	PMSDATA:	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_Bnnn_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO	X	If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end.
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
b) Directory: PMSDATA:	X	
c) File generation: Hit enter	X	
d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data	X	
e) TAS: Y	X	
f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX	X	
g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both	X	
0 unless either probe known to be faulty	X	
h) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown	X	Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log.
i) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown	X	
j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5	X	
k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud	X	Note the particle type
11 if known to be in water cloud	X	
8 if known to be in mixed-phase	X	
8 if unknown	X	
l) Coefficient choice: 2	X	
m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D	x	NO DATA BLOCKS !!
10) In PVWAVE	n/a	Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 9h) and 9j).
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!		
ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D'		
iii) exit		
11) MODIFY	n/a	No data blocks
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D		
b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX		
c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name		
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		
12) CHECKS:	n/a	No data blocks
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B170****Date:**

D) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing	X	
Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	X X	
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW	X	Note the min size channel Note the volume flow rate
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT	X	
c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP	X	
Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary)	X	
PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii)	X	
d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1	1	
If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here		
e) Calibration volume flow rate:		
Use the most recent value.		
Calibration files to be stored in ?????		
Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm ³ /sec	1.6 ml/sec	
f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d)	0	
g) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown	0 ok	Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log.
h) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown	240000 ok	
3) In PVWAVE	X	Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 2g) and 2h).
i) enter:	X	
!PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X	
Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!	X	
ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat'	X	
,'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp'	X	
iii) exit	X	
4) MODIFY	X	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp	X	
b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX	X	
c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name	MFDE	
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	X	All looks fine the MFD

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B170

Date: DD/MM/YY

E) NetCDF file preparation and ftp to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Run TAREXEC:MFD_BADC		
For inputs below, just press ENTER to use defaults		Defaults in [square brackets]
a) MFD to convert: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX b) version number for BADC: r[0] c) Names file: TARDIS_ROOT:[CALTEXT.NETCDF]CP_NAMES.TXT d) Directory: [DATA_ROOT:[NETCDF]] e) File prefix: [core-cloud-phy_faam] f) File suffix: [] g) File for output: [core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.nc]		As from 4c) above default NOT the default default default default Default name is generated
2) Ftp transfer to BADC		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stage 1) creates two files: - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.nc - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.txt The *.txt file should be renamed to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn_descrip.txt but this cannot be done on VMS as the filename is too long You should do it if the file is first transferred to a PC, or after it has been uploaded to the appropriate "incoming" directory at BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd /incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core d) copy *.txt file as ascii e) copy *.nc and *2D-IMAGES.pdf files as binary		

F) BACKUP PROCEDURES		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Backup the intermediate files created in PMSDATA:		
a) zip "-V" PMSDATA:Bnnn*. * outdir:Bnnn_PMSDATA.zip Note that the uppercase "-V" option is important to preserve the VMS file characteristics when files are restored from this zip file.		Note destination directory "outdir"

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** Bnnn**Date:** DD/MM/YY

A) Raw data transfer to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer raw data files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt Bnnn_FFSSP.raw Bnnn_FFSSP_House_1.hse etc.		
2) Zip these file on the PC -output file: core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawffssp.zip		
3) Transfer SEADAS Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
4) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip) - rename Bnnn.zip to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawseadas.zip		
5) ftp to BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd incoming/faam/campaign_raw d) bin e) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawffssp.zip f) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawseadas.zip		Binary data transfer

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT ON	OFF	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
				1	2	3	4	5	
1019	1020	095	19.91	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			19.08	0.18	0.33	0.51	0.73	1.11	S
			18.14	818	1179	1117	1760	2096	D
			17.57	516	525	575	659	659	B
			16.80	2264	2266	2267	2275	2275	R
			980.9	980.9	980.9	980.9	980.9	P	
105345			20.26	0.18	0.33	0.50	0.76	1.16	S
			19.61	709	1025	1836	1471	2150	D
			18.82	358	364	364	483	615	B
			17.98	2217	2219	2219	2214	2214	R
			16.92	1016.3	1016.2	1016.2	1016.2	1016.2	P
11530			20.74	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			20.05	0.18	0.31	0.51	0.72	1.09	S
			19.23	593	755	1097	1656	1749	D
			18.44	284	286	317	400	540	B
			17.40	2198	2210	2233	2276	2295	R
			1016.3	1016	1016	1016	1016	P	
113745			21.67	0.18	0.32	0.51	0.72	1.01	S
			20.79	676	652	1076	1427	1893	D
			20.00	305	309	322	394	509	B
			19.23	2269	2261	2257	2251	2234	R
			18.21	1015.6	1015.6	1015.6	1015.6	1015.6	P
1209				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			22.57	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.71	1.09	S
			22.09	667	697	1201	1610	2317	D
			21.13	325	335	368	368	578	B
			20.38	2284	2284	2281	2281	2281	R
			19.37	1010.4	1010.4	1010.4	1010.4	1010.4	P
123030				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			23.26	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.70	1.1	S
			22.49	839	1235	1173	1646	2151	D
			21.72	326	335	377	466	636	B
			20.95	2232	2222	2224	2218	2217	R
			20.04	1010.3	1010.3	1010.3	1010.3	1010.3	P
125230				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			23.70	0.17	0.31	0.50	0.71	1.07	S
			22.95	655	968	1399	1364	1871	D
			22.18	317	328	368	368	574	B
			21.53	2276	2283	2291	2300	2304	R
			20.37	1010.3	1010.3	1010.2	1010.3	1010.2	P
131450			24.05	0.17	0.31	0.50	0.70	1.05	S
			23.28	567	1278	1460	2080	2047	D
			22.55	344	356	356	495	621	B
			21.75	2337	2338	2340	2342	2342	R
			20.84	987.4	987.5	987.5	987.5	987.5	P

BT

*

ARIES flight log

Flight: *B170*

Location: *~200 nm S. Dakar*

page 1 of 6

Date: *11-2-6*

Operator(s): *VANCE*

Resolution: *1*

Gain A: *2* B: *2*

Notes: *Preflight OK, flight has intermittent hangs & 60 scans/min.*

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
0737 ~	<i>pan</i>	<i>b170</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>OK flight rec. on 0740</i>
084149	<i>"</i>	<i>b170a</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>26</i>	<i>~21</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>-189.9</i>	<i>25.2</i>	<i>CH1x1</i>	<i>(have had ptg array off for T)</i>
084610 N	<i>"</i>	<i>b170b</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>30</i>	<i>~23</i>	<i>20.1</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>26</i>	<i>IR x1</i>	<i>~10 secs actual view</i>
084829	<i>"</i>	<i>b170c</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>30</i>	<i>24</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>26</i>	<i>CH2x1</i>	
085111	<i>"</i>	<i>b170d</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>30</i>	<i>~25</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>26</i>	<i>Z1x1</i>	
085223	<i>"</i>	<i>b170e</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>30</i>	<i>~25</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>26</i>	<i>N1x1</i>	<i>(Pointing array off after)</i>
095457	<i>T/O</i>									
0957										<i>(off to cool -190 70 software scans -> 60 software restart</i>
100010	<i>P1</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>O</i>				<i>-190</i>	<i>30</i>		<i>still at 60 -> back to 122 @ 100100</i>
100525	<i>"</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>44</i>	<i>30.6</i>	<i>21</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>29.9</i>		<i>Scan fluctuating -> 60 occ. TAT 17 Td</i>
101058	<i>P1 ↑</i>	<i>B170G</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>30</i>	<i>21</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>CH1x1</i>	<i>EPI, SP2 @ 101121</i>
101400	<i>P2 ↓</i>	<i>B170H?</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>"</i>	<i>broken high-medium & low cloud</i>
101905	<i>R1</i>	<i>H</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>70</i>	<i>30</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>CH1x1</i>	
102018	<i>R1</i>	<i>B170</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>30</i>	<i>Z1x4</i>	<i>in cloud tops</i>
102159										<i>HUNG, about & keep</i>
		<i>I</i>								<i>Scan 60! about</i>
102433		<i>K</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>70</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>29</i>	<i>CH1x1</i>	
1025(20)?	<i>R1</i>	<i>B170L</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>30</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>-190</i>		<i>Z1x4</i>	<i>Scan 60 & Hung @ 102610</i>
		<i>M</i>							<i>Z1x1</i>	<i>" "</i>

R1: 'Transit'

ARIES flight log

(0800) 1405

Flight: B170

Location: ~200mm S of Dakar

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Date: 11-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
103130	R1	B170o	C	71	30	18	-190	28	CH1x1	all restarted
1032(30?)	R1	B170P	O	71	31	17	-190	26	Z1x2	Hung. in second
103436	P3	B170Q	O	71	31				CH1x1	Scans 60 & back
105336	SR2.1	B170R	C	71	31	25	-190	31	CH1x1	R2: B → C
105449	R2.1	B170S	O	71	31	25	-190	31	Z1x4	R2 21°C TAT
105830	R2.1	B170T	O/C	71	33	26	-190	30	CH1x1	
105931	"	B170U	C	71	33	27	-190	31	CH1x1	
110038	"	B170V	O	71	33	27	-190	31	Z1x2	
110330	"	B170W	C	71	34	27	-190	30	CH1x1	Noise 16MS on HBB?
110440	"	B170X	C	71	33	27	-190	31	CH1x1	
110555	"	B170Y	O	71	34	27	-190	31	Z1x1	(TAT on 2.1 292-7295 some big peaks (2K) near end.)
110700 110936 120900	"	B170Z	O	71	34	27	-190	31	Z1x1	aborted EOR
111009	R 2.2	B1701	C	71	34	28	-190	31	CH1x1	
111118	R2.2	B1702	O	70	34	27	-190	31	Z1x3	
111500	TURN FR2.2	B1703	C	71	36	28	-190	31	CH1x1	actually SR2.3
111630	R2.3	B1704	O	71	35	27	-190	31	Z1x4	
112100	R2.3	B1705	C	71	36	27	-190	31	CH1x1	
102212	R2.3	B1706	C	71	36	27	-190	31	Z1x3	

2355
R371208

ARIES flight log

Flight: B170

Location:

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Date: 11-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B:2

Notes: R2 @ 2000' R3 @ FL045

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
112705 112708	R2.3	B1707	c	71	36	28	-190		CH1x1	
112726	R2.3	B1708	o	71	36	28	-190	31	Z1x4	ER 113006
113225 113240	R2.4	B1709	c	71	37	27	-190	32	CH1x1	
113245	R2.4	C170a	o	71	37	28	-190	32	Z1x3	
113525	ER2.4	C170B	c	71	37	28	-189.9	32	CH1x1	
113734?	R2.5	C170C	o	71	37	28	-190	32	Z1x4	turn 113910
114240	R2.5	C170D	c	71	38	28	-190	32	CH1x1	
11 ? ops	R2.5	C170E	o	71	37	28	-190	32	Z1x3	
114740	R2.5	C170F	c	71	38	28	-190	32	CH1x1	
114850	R2.5	C170G	o	71	37	29	-190	33	Z1x3	
115237	R2.5	C170H	c	71	37	28	-190	33	CH1x1	
115420ish	R2.5	C170I	o	71	37	28	-190	32	Z1x1	
115619	ER2.5	C170J	c	71	37	28	-190	32	Z1x1	Software/plbg restarted.
1210	R3.1	C170K	c	70	40					Making this run w plbg off & IR shutter open to try & cool cold target. TAT 20° No gas
121728	R3.1	C170K	c	71	41	27	-190	35	CH1x1	
121928	R3.1	C170L	o	71	40	28	-190	34	Z1x4	760 @ 1220 after about
1222~	R3.1	C170M	o	71	41	28	-190	33	Z1x2	608 back to 122
122458	R3.1	C170N	.	71	41	28	-190	33	CH1x1	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B170

Location: S of DAKAR

page 5 of 6

Date: 11-2-5

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B:2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
133359	R4.	C1707	C	77	31	21	-190	31	CHI	Restarted
133509	R	C1708	O						Z1+3	Hung 1237?
133930	R	C1709	C	71	31	21	-190	30	CHI X1	
134045	R	D170a	O	70	31.5	21	-190	31	Z1 X1	
		b							CHI oops	aborted
134254		D170c	O	70	32	21	-190	29	Z1 X1	hung.
1346	reinstalling software from 'fastnetu' pointing away off during									
1350		D								Restart
135235		D170E	C	71	31	21	-190	31	CHI X1	
135352	R	D170F	O	7					Z1 X1	fell over & hung
		G							Z1 X1	
135555		H								
135820	R4.4	I	C/O						Z1 X1	Restart software
140012		D170J	C	71	31	20	-190	30	CHI X1	
140124	R 4.5	D170K	O	71	31	21	-190	30	Z1 X3	Hung after 1.
		L								→ 60! hung
140440	~	D170M	O	70	31	20	-190	28	Z1 X1	" "
140830	~	D170N	C	71	31	20	-190	30	CHI X1	Software restart.
141007M	~	D170O	O	71	34	20	-190	30	Z1 X1	hung @ 60 scans

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B170	Date	11/02/06	Operat or(s)	Ian Rule	log page	1	of	3
Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS									
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				
0850						SWS vis and nir ok, run from rack pc. SHIMS vis only ok run from laptop			
0855						Laptop time set to DRS time			
095449	P1					T/o dakar and start P1			
Note that video recorder is u/s for this flight									
095733	P1		Zen+6 fwd	200	500	SWS Start recording	X		
095957	P1		"	75	200		X		
100721	P1		-	50		SHIMS started initially with shutter closed, box temp = 14		X	
101122	P1/P2	FL160				End P1, start P2, significant cloud above			
1013						SHIMS dropped out			
101744	P2		-	75		SHIMS back up, shutter closed initially		X	
101901	P2/R1	FL95				End profile start run, in aerosol			
102039	R1	FL95	Zen+6 fwd	75	200	SWS dark cal, box temp = 12	x		
102235	R1	FL95	-	75		SHIMS dark cal, box temp = 11		x	
1024						SHIMS dropped out		x	
102911	R1	FL95	-	75		SHIMS back up, shutter initially closed, box temp = 10		x	
103402	R1/P3	FL95				End run, start profile, decend through aerosol layer, significant upper cloud			
103543	P3			75	200	Shutters closed on both SWS and shims for approx 15 s	x	x	
104504	P3/P4	50'				End profile, start next, box temp = 10			
104850	P4	2000'				End profile			
105200		2000'	Zen+ 6fwd	75	200	Shutters closed on both SWS and SHIMSfor approx 30 s, box temp = 9	x	x	
105335	R2.1	2000'				Start run, box temp =12			
110320	R2.1	2000'	"	50	200	Change SWS integ time	x		
110838						End run, shutters closed in turn			
110940	R2.2	2000'				Start run			
1110			Zen+ 6fwd	50	200		x		
1110				75				x	
111426	R2.2	2000'				End run, shutters closed in turn			
111506	R2.3	2000				Start run			
113007						End run shutters closed in turn			
113107	R2.4	2000'				Start run			
1131	R2.4			50	200		x		
1131	R2.4			75				x	
1133						SWS NIR dropped out, too cold? Box temp = 7			
1135						Re initialised SWS	x		
113602	R2.4			50	200	End run sws ok, box temp = 9, shims shutter closed in turn	x		
113719	R2.5					Start run			
1137	R2.5			75				x	
115531						End run, shutters closed in turn			
115608	P5					Start profile			

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B170	Date	11/02/06	Operat or(s)	Ian Rule	log page	2	of	3
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Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				
1156	P5		Zen +6fwd	50	200		x		
1156	P5		-	75				x	
120058		4500'				End profile			
120835	R3.1	4500				Start run			
122339						End run, shutters closed in turn			
122434	R3.2	4500				Start run			
1224				50	200		x		
1224				75				x	
122936						End run, shutters closed in turn			
123029	R3.3	4500'				Start run			
124508						End run, shutters closed in turn			
124631	R3.4	4500'				Start run			
1246				50	200		x		
1246				75				x	
125010				30	200	Change integ time for SWS	x		
125131						End run, shutters closed in turn			
125221	R3.5	4500				Start run			
1252	R3.5	4500'	Zen +6fwd	30	200	Maintaining box temp between 12 and 10	X		
1252	R3.5	4500'	-	75		Still in aerosol layer, significant cloud above		x	
130722						End run, shutters closed in turn			
130802	P6	4500'				Start profile			
131417	P6/R4.1	FL84				End profile, start run			
1314	R4.1	FL84	Zen +6fwd	30	200		x		
1314	R4.1	FL84	-	75				x	
133037	R4.2					End run, shutters closed in turn			
133137	R4.2	FL84				Start run			
133639						End run, shutters closed in turn			
133748	R4.3	FL84				Start run			
1340	R4.3	FL84	Zen +6fwd	30	200		X		
1340	R4.3	FL84	-	75		Cloud above patchier here		X	
135250						End run, shutters closed in turn			
135351	R4.4	FL84				Start run			
135853						End run, shutters closed in turn			
135946	R4.5	FL84				Start run			
141445						End run, shutters closed in turn			
141640	P7	FL84				Start profile up			
142020		FL120				End profile, shutters closed briefly			
142039	P8	FL120				Start P8			
1420	P8		Zen +6f	30	200				
1420	P8			75					
143328	P8/P9	50'				End profile, start next			
143826		FL50				End profile, shutters closed			
1440						Instruments shut down			
1440						Laptop time = DRS time +/- 0			
145336						Land Dakar			

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B170

Date:

11 FEB 2006

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Whatman QMA (top)	Bottom inlet	90 mm 0.4 µm Nuclepore followed by a 90 mm paper (top)
Except for				

Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [I]	Comments
Filters run1	B170Q1	----	----	Top	10:56:00	11:09:00	R2.1	1723	1.9 kft
Filters run1	B170N1	----	----	Bottom	10:56:00	11:09:00	R2.1	1117	1.9 kft
Filters run2	B170Q2	----	----	Top	11:17:00	11:31:00	R2.3	1861	1.9 kft
Filters run2	B170N2	----	----	Bottom	11:17:00	11:31:00	R2.3	1138	1.9 kft
Filters run3	B170Q3	----	----	Top	11:37:00	11:55:00	R2.5	2536	1.9 kft
Filters run3	B170N3	----	----	Bottom	11:37:00	11:55:00	R2.5	1524	1.9 kft
Filters run4	B170Q4	----	----	Top	12:10:00	12:25:00	R3.1	1909	4.5 kft
Filters run4	B170N4	----	----	Bottom	12:10:00	12:25:00	R3.1	1145	4.5 kft
Filters run5	B170Q5	----	----	Top	12:30:00	12:46:00	R3.3	2037	4.5 kft
Filters run5	B170N5	----	----	Bottom	12:30:00	12:46:00	R3.3	1203	4.5 kft, filter came away from o-ring
Filters run6	B170Q6	----	----	Top	12:54:00	13:09:00	R3.5	1427	4.5 kft
Filters run6	B170N6	----	----	Bottom	12:54:00	13:09:00	R3.5	1222	4.5 kft
Filters run7	B170Q7	----	----	Top	13:14:00	13:34:00	R4.1	1323	8.4 kft
Filters run7	B170N7	----	----	Bottom	13:14:00	13:34:00	R4.1	1118	8.4 kft
Filters run8	B170Q7	----	----	Top	13:35:00	13:49:00	R4.3/R4.4	1069	8.4 kft
Filters run8	B170N7	----	----	Bottom	13:35:00	13:49:00	R4.3/R4.4	1022	8.4 kft
Filters run8	B170Q9								Blank
Filters run8	B170N13								Blank

All BC filters: foil was not replaced over stack after exposure

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.170**.....

 Date 11/2/06
 RH' 12.6

 Operator's name: J. Bowles.....

 Page 1 of 2

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
10:05								WET NEF ON PUMP @ 15°C
10:44	R3				68	↑35		
10:15		FL 018	12.5		73.2	↓15 (14)		√
11:03	2.1	"	12.6		49.8	↑250	15.14	
11:06	2.1	"	12.7		53.5	↑350		
11:11	2.2	"	12.6		68.4	↑45		
11:12:44		"	12.5		84.1	↓15.0		
11:29:41		"	12.6		49.6	↑25		
11:32:42		"	12.5		57.1	↑35		
11:35:44		"	12.6		72.1	↑45		
11:43:00		"	12.7		84.5	↓15		
11:54:07		"	12.6		48.2	↑25		
11:52:06		→ 005	12.0		51.5	↑35		
12:02:06		4500	12.6		59.7	↑45		
12:10:09		"	12.5		77.1	↓15		
12:25:09		"	12.5		37.4	↑25		
12:30:22		"	12.4		62.4	↑35		
12:33:21		"	12.5		54	↑45		
12:39:41	3.3	"	12.5		73.8	↓15		
12:53:40			12.5		38.7	↑25		

Bags are numbers 1-140 and tubes are the other samples

Date	11/02/06			Flight#	B170		
T.O.	09:54:50	Land	14:53:35	04:58:45			Jim McQuaid (ULeeds)
Tube/Bag #	START	END	Alt. (ft)	Sample Time	Flow	Vol	Comments
62186	10:50:50	10:58:40		00:07:50	300	2350	
27	11:02	11:03:10		00:01:10		n/a	
92	11:06:10	11:07:20		00:01:10		n/a	
25	11:16:10	11:17:10		00:01:00		n/a	
9508	11:17:30	11:36:00		00:18:30		n/a	BLANK
67	11:19:20	11:20:10		00:00:50		n/a	
99	11:21:30	11:22:30		00:01:00		n/a	
67605	11:23:30	11:34		00:10:30	350	3675	
2	11:41:10	11:42:30		00:01:20		n/a	
83	12:09:40	12:11:10		00:01:30		n/a	
14784	12:16:40	12:23:30		00:06:50	300	2050	one end was loose
CO12906	12:31:30	12:44		00:12:30	200	2500	
42		12:57:20		12:57:20		n/a	
62346	13:03:20	13:16		00:13:30	200	2700	
67689	13:20:10	13:30:30		00:10:20	200	2067	
20	13:42:40	13:43:50		00:01:10		n/a	
67630	13:46:30	13:54		00:07:30	200	1500	
DO18257	14:00	14:15		00:15:00	200	3000	

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 170

Date: 11th February 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	N	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	N		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	Y
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	Y
		AMS	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	Y	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	Y
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	Y	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	Y	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B170

Date: 11 February 2006

Instruments

1. Upper and Lower Pyrometers – signal noisy
2. JW not operated
- 3.
- 4.

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom Calls

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B170:

Log	Reason
PSAP	The instrument may not have been operated
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
VACC	No log is taken/provided for VACC
PAN	No log is taken/provided for PAN

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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